

Quality planting material production of three major timber trees in agroforestry: Seed and nursery techniques

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Integration of trees with crop cultivation, livestock production, and other farm activities is popularly known as "agroforestry," and woody perennials are the core of this integrated farming system because it provides multiple outputs or benefits to the stakeholders. A higher yield from the trees could be obtained with reliable planting material and good management practices. Generally, agroforestry is considered a subset of trees outside of forests (TOF), and most of the cultivation practices are present on private farmlands, wastelands, community lands, etc., but harsh environmental conditions in these sites will have a severe impact on the quality and quantity of the outputs. So, in this regard, we need good-quality planting materials to meet the various demands of

farmers as well as ensure quality raw materials for wood-based industries.

Quality Planting Material (QPM) may be defined as "the production of uniform, healthy, disease-free planting material raised through seed or vegetative methods with an overall goal to raise the physiological and phytosanitary quality of the plant and make it available to stakeholders to increase productivity." Particularly for economically relevant timber species, quality plant material (QPM) from agroforestry species is necessary. To produce high-quality planting materials on a large scale, it is important to have a thorough understanding of seed and nursery processes.

Seeds of *Tectona grandis* Seeds of *Dalbergia latifolia* Seeds of *Swietenia macrophylla*

(Source: <https://www.google.com/wikipedia>)

Seed technology of *Tectona grandis***Seed characteristics**

Marble-white, egg-shaped seeds having a 1-2 cm length, 1 cm width, and 1, 433 to 3, 527 fruits/kg in seed weight. Seeds are generally dispersed by insects.

Seed collection

Typically, the cleared area is where seeds are gathered. We can also physically harvest seeds from trees by shaking the branches with a long pole equipped with a hook.

Seed processing

By rubbing the seeds in gunny bags forcefully, the bladder-like calyx is removed. By winnowing, the calyx parts are separated (Chacko et al., 2002). Fruits are soaked in water for 72 hours, then mixed with equal parts of sand and small stones (1:1:1), before being placed in a machine with two revolving discs (100 rpm) with a slightly concave shape and ribbed surface to remove the pericarp and create a more uniformly shaped and brittle material. This processed material is put into a second component that has two parallel cylinders that rotate at 520 rpm and have a diameter of 35 mm. This second component crushes the fruits and releases the seeds.

Seed storage

Seeds are orthodox in nature. For two to three years, seeds can be dry stored in metal tins, airtight plastic containers, or gunny bags (Chacko et al., 2002). When seeds are kept in airtight metal containers as opposed to loose bags, their viability lasts longer, and they germinate more successfully.

Viability period

Enduring for more than a year (Chacko et al., 2002)

Seed pre-treatment

Teak seeds with rocky seed coats need to be pre-treated to germinate more quickly. The germination of seeds is improved by letting termites consume the mesocarp, leaving behind seeds with stony endocarp, and by immersing the seeds in a cow dung solution for 24 hours.

Germination details

Epigeous type of germination and germination percentage is goes up to 75 to 77 (Chacko et al., 2002). Germination period ranges mostly 8 to 60 days.

Nursery technique of *Tectona grandis*

Traditionally, between the summer and the rainy season, seeds are put on raised nursery beds (30 cm height). Compared to root trainers and sand medium, nursery beds are the best place for teak drupes to sprout. The seeds are planted in 20 centimetre raised nursery beds, spaced 5 cm apart in lines 10 cm apart, and covered with 1 cm of sand. A 5 cm top layer of sand with well-rotted FYM should be present in the beds. The seedbeds are irrigated three times each day until 75 days after sowing is reached for the end of the process. Compared to survival rate of stumps (58-96%), container seedlings have a greater survival rate (96-100%). Root coiling and multiple shoot development were additional characteristics of container seedlings, and their management was not economical. As a result, it encourages the use of stumps. At 7 months of age, stumps should be between 1 and 2 cm in size. From seedlings that are one year old, 2.5 cm shoot length, 15 to 20 cm root length, and 1 to 2 cm diameter at the thickest region of the root are prepared. Root trainer seedlings, which are 60 to 90 days old, and polybag seedlings, which are 40

to 60 days old, are also utilised for planting (Chacko et al., 2002).

Seed Technology of *Dalbergia latifolia*

Seed characteristics

Reddish brown in colour and have a seed length of 5-7 mm, seed width of 3-5 mm, and seed thickness of 1-2 mm and 21, 000 to 40,000 seeds/kg in seed weight.

Seed collection

By pruning the branches of the trees, ripe dark brown pods can be harvested

Seed processing

The seeds are manually taken from the dried pods by crushing them, or the pods can be baked in an oven at 50°C for 3.5 hours to extract the seeds.

Seed storage

Seeds are probably orthodox in nature. The pods are kept for six months in earthened pots and gunny bags. Seeds that are improperly dried before storage typically lose viability quickly (Chacko et al., 2002).

Viability period

Enduring for six months (Chacko et al., 2002).

Seed pre-treatment

Soaking in cold water for 24 hours prior to seeding will help with germination (Chacko et al., 2002). At lower concentrations (1–20 ppm), IAA can increase plant percentages and germination by up to 10%.

Germination details

Epigeous type of germination and germination percentage is goes up to 80. Germination period ranges mostly 7 to 21 days (Chacko et al., 2002).

Nursery technique of *Dalbergia latifolia*

In vermiculite-lined germination trays, seeds are sown and then watered. When the seedlings are between 5 and 6 cm tall,

they are pricked out into plastic bags about 22.5 x 17.5 cm and filled with potting soil. *Rhizoctonia solani* causes seedling collar rot, which can be prevented in nurseries by using the fungicide carboxin (1.0 percent) (Chacko et al., 2002). Seedlings planted in root trainers using potting medium made of 60% compost, 30% sand, and 10% soil show great growth.

Seed Technology of *Swietenia macrophylla*

Seed characteristics

Flat winged brown seeds have a seed length of 8.3 cm, seed width of 2.5 cm, and 1, 600 to 2, 300 seeds/kg in seed weight.

Seed collection

Before they dehisce, mature fruits are harvested from the trees before their grain turns brown from grey grain.

Seed processing

The seeds are manually harvested after the fruits have been sun dried till they open (Chacko et al., 2002)

Seed storage

Orthodox; Intermediate (Chacko et al., 2002). The viability of seeds has an intermediate seed storage behaviour. Could well be preserved in the plastic bags at 10°C for more than two years.

Viability period

It is viable for up to three months in typical circumstances

Seed pre-treatment

Pre-treatment is not necessary. It is advantageous to de-wing before planting

Germination details

Hypogeal type of germination with germination percentage is about 90 and germination period 10-112 days (Chacko et al., 2002).

Nursery technique of *Swietenia macrophylla*

Vermiculite-filled germination trays are used to horizontally sow seeds at a depth of 2 cm. When the seedlings reach a height of 15 cm, they are moved into polythene bags measuring 22.5 x 17.5 cm that are filled with soil or root trainers. Three months after being potted, the seedlings are prepared for planting (Chacko et al., 2002).

Reference

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